

SCIENCE IN THE CLASSROOM, FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD AND PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

IV: SCIENCE AS A LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes that science education in childhood can be conceived as the acquisition of a second language: the language of science. As noted in previous works, this language assumes the functions of Kantian categories of space, time, and causality, which allow both the representation of the world in the mind and the description of that representation. Within this framework, scientific knowledge can be understood as a symbolic system in which each signifier carries a double meaning: the semantic value, which identifies the observable, and the mathematical object that describes its behavior and transformations. These mathematical objects may be scalars, vectors, tensors, functions, or even more abstract structures such as transformation groups, since many physical laws are determined by symmetries that are precisely expressed through these groups.

From this perspective, teaching science means teaching its own language—an evolved form of symbolic representation with its own grammar, the very instrument of scientific thought. As with natural languages, learning begins with simple associations between a word and an object and gradually progresses toward more complex structures, through experiments, the conceptualization of magnitudes, and mental simulations.

Keywords: Science learning; Mathematical language; Mentalese; Universal grammar; Piaget; Galileo; Cognitive development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Taking into account what has been presented in previous articles of this series, we now have the intellectual background necessary to propose an approach to teaching science in the early stages of education. Teaching consists of guiding students in the construction of a mental representation of the external world that, although simplified, incorporates the essential elements for it to function analogously to the real world. Einstein (1936) expressed this idea by stating that science is the recreation in the mind of a replica of that part of the world accessible to our senses, through intellectual structures invented by human beings.

Within this framework, the analysis and organization of information that reaches the mind through the senses are carried out through *mentalese* (Fodor, J. A., 1975), the language of thought. If, in accordance with Galileo's definition, we understand science as the representation in the mind of that part of the world that can be expressed through mathematical language, then scientific knowledge is built through a special language in which each signifier is associated, in addition to a concept, with a mathematical object—such as real numbers, complex numbers, or tensors—that defines and determines its behavior.

Thus, teaching science is equivalent to teaching a language with its own characteristics. And, like any language, its learning must begin progressively and from early childhood, taking advantage of the critical stages of cognitive development. This process involves carrying out classroom experiments, conceptualizing magnitudes, and practicing mental simulations, conceived as exercises that facilitate the acquisition of this specialized language, which can be regarded as a true second language.

2. THE SPECIFIC LANGUAGE OF SCIENCE

Once an agreement has been established on the meanings of knowledge, thought, intelligence, and learning (see previous articles in this series), we turn to Saussure (1916) to complement this theoretical framework, showing how verbal language makes it possible to connect the mental representations of different individuals. According to his theory of the linguistic sign, each person associates a signifier (the sound of a word) with a signified (the concept that has been internally constructed), housed within a neural network of the brain. When two people hear the same signifier—for example, *yellow*—each activates in their mind the corresponding concept, even if their sensory experiences of that color are not identical. In this way, language acts as a bridge between subjective representations, enabling the communication of ideas.

However, since Galileo, the language of science has required an expansion of this system of signs (Galileo, 1623/1957). Let us recall the idea that the book of nature is written in mathematical characters, an idea that fostered the development of physics as the paradigm of rigorous science, meeting the most demanding criteria of truth. But, as a counterpart, scientific knowledge became restricted to the world of magnitudes, that is, to those quantifiable aspects of reality that can be measured and expressed mathematically through equations between measures, between numbers.

Extending this theory to the scientific sign, for example to the weight of a body, we observe that each signifier acquires a double meaning: a semantic one (the force with which the Earth attracts it), linked to the real world, and an operational one (it is a vector), which defines its nature as a mathematical object, existing only in our mind but determining its nature and the laws it obeys. This conceptual reorganization requires an educational process in which students learn to translate concepts from ordinary language into entities with mathematically defined behavior.

This dual structure is extremely important and very interesting from the point of view of the philosophy of knowledge. If we want to distribute 100 euros (from the real world) among 20 people (also from the real world), we first bring the two numbers, 100 and 20, into our mind. There, we manipulate these numbers according to the mathematical rules of division, disregarding what those numbers represent, and obtain as a result the number 5. We conclude the process by bringing that number back into the real world and restoring its meaning as the amount of euros given to each of the beneficiaries.

Let us analyze the process. The problem arises in the real world. The relevant magnitudes are determined, also in the real world: the amount to be distributed and the number of people among whom it is distributed. These magnitudes are then assigned their corresponding mathematical objects (real numbers in this case), which are treated according to their mathematical nature, stripped of their real-world meaning. Once the corresponding mathematical operations are carried out (in the world of ideas, Plato would say), we bring the result back to the real world, where they recover their identity (euros and people), thereby solving the problem. And all this is done using the scientific language (with two meanings) as the programming language of the brain.

This process is common to all human activity, not only scientific but also mental. An architect designs in his mind the building he wants to construct. He does so by imagining it composed of straight lines, circles, rectangles, etc., all of them perfect geometric ideas. Once the problems involved in constructing a building have been resolved in his mind, he returns to the real world where he reproduces his idea with real materials, although the straight lines and circles will not, by any means, have the beauty and perfection they had in his mind.

Beyond Galileo

But fortunately, science does not remain confined to the world of magnitudes. For centuries, mathematics was understood mainly as the science of magnitudes. It was used to measure lengths, areas, or volumes in geometry, calculate times and velocities in physics, or solve numerical operations in arithmetic and algebra. That is, it was above all an instrument for working with quantities. However, in the 19th century, the French mathematician Évariste Galois (along with contemporaries such as Cauchy and Abel) introduced a radical idea: what is essential in mathematics is not so much the measurement or value of a magnitude, but the way in which mathematical objects relate to and transform into one another. From this idea was born the concept of mathematical

structure, which we find in examples such as symmetry groups, permutations, or set theory.

This change was a genuine revolution because it expanded the field of application of mathematics. And, strictly following Galileo's criterion of calling science that which can be expressed in mathematical language, the expansion of mathematics pulled the sciences along with it, increasing their field of application in unimaginable ways. From then on, mathematics was no longer only used to measure and calculate, but also to describe patterns and structures present in all sciences. In physics, for example, fundamental laws are formulated in terms of symmetries; in chemistry, group theory helps explain the shape of molecules; and in computer science, modern cryptography is based on algebraic structures. Thanks to this step, mathematics went from being a language limited to the quantitative to becoming a universal tool, capable of explaining how very different natural and technological phenomena are organized and function.

All these considerations lead us to propose that, since language—in the sense proposed by Chomsky, Fodor, and Saussure—contains the very essence of the process of mentally representing the world, its union with mathematical language transforms it into a tool capable of organizing reality so that it can be represented in the mind, as well as describing it through a symbolic system that constitutes science. The language of science is science itself.

Therefore, teaching science can be understood as teaching a second language capable of handling reality using Platonic ideas—such as vectors, wave functions, symmetries, rotations, groups, rings, algebras, etc.—which, despite being only ideas, determine the behavior of the real world.

3. TEACHING SCIENCE AS A LANGUAGE

The considerations outlined above have led us, as stated, to identify scientific language with science itself and, consequently, to approach teaching science as if it were a second language: the language of science.

With regard to content planning, nothing seems more natural than to follow the history of science, which is necessarily constructivist in itself, aligning paradigm shifts with the significant changes in students' cognitive development—changes that are well known to teachers at these educational stages.

3.1. TEACHING SCIENCE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

According to specialists, there are two fundamental processes for learning a second language (L2): acquisition and learning. Acquisition occurs naturally and unconsciously when a child is immersed in an environment where the language is spoken, as happens in bilingual families or in migratory contexts (Krashen, 1982). Learning, by contrast, takes place when the child has already mastered a mother tongue and faces the L2 as another language to be consciously incorporated, mediated, and supported by the L1.

As for the teaching of science, no cases of acquisition by immersion have been documented, since it is unlikely that a child would grow up in a household environment dominated by scientific discourse. This contrasts with disciplines such as music—as in the case of Mozart—or the visual arts, where early and everyday exposure can indeed favor acquisition (Bruner, 1960; Gardner, 1983).

However, if the teaching of an L2 (or of science as L2) begins between the ages of 3 and 7—the so-called “golden window” for language learning—it is possible to achieve native or near-native mastery, provided that exposure is sufficient. Between ages 7 and 12, although brain plasticity decreases, children can still attain high communicative competence and grammatical structure.

From this perspective, we propose that science instruction should begin at the preschool stage, adapting to the logical-cognitive capacities of the students (López Sancho & Gómez Díaz, 2016). And, as with language learning, scientific exposure should not be limited to what the child already understands. As Vygotsky notes, children select their zone of proximal development from among the information they receive, choosing the stimuli that are meaningful to them in order to progress in their learning.

In fact, when it comes to spoken language, no one would think of saying: *Do not talk to the baby; she doesn't understand because she doesn't yet know how to speak*. Everyone knows that one learns to speak by listening and speaking. Similarly, one learns to think scientifically by doing and seeing science in action, even before fully understanding it.

By considering science as a symbolic system, we can clearly identify its basic components: concepts, magnitudes, structures, laws, models, and paradigms, which we have already discussed. Thus, when planning a teaching unit, we can identify its specific ontology, that is, the framework in which learning will take place, defined by the concepts that will be present. This identification allows for the design of didactic sequences in which students progressively discover—and at the same time enact—the processes of observation, experimentation, law formulation, and theory building, assimilating them as part of the scientific language with which to describe and structure experience.

3.2. THE CASE OF ARCHIMEDES' PRINCIPLE

For greater clarity, we will describe the method using the pedagogical resource of case-based teaching, applying it to Archimedes' principle in relation to water. The principle (in reality an experimental law as well as the result of a thought experiment) constitutes an excellent example of scientific inquiry in school and provides great satisfaction to students when they come to understand the process of scientific discovery for themselves. As Bruner (1960) notes, the act of discovery awakens curiosity and generates intrinsic pleasure by revealing the cause-and-effect relationships hidden in nature.

Unfortunately, Archimedes' principle often proves quite opaque to children when presented in its verbal, descriptive form, leading to situations where they can recite the statement from memory yet understand almost none of its words.

The *CSIC en la Escuela* program proposes addressing the teaching of science by first giving meaning to the words—that is, to the ontology. This is equivalent to the construction, by the students, of the necessary concepts for meaningful learning, achieved through direct manipulation of real objects. From these concepts, students are guided toward the construction of progressively more abstract mental representations of reality, which are therefore more powerful in discovering and replicating the behavior of reality (López Sancho & Gómez Díaz, 2016; Novak, 1998; Piaget, 1970).

3.3. DETERMINING THE ONTOLOGY OF THE PROBLEM

Let us now imagine a group of children who are not yet familiar with Archimedes' principle. To prepare the lesson, the teacher must first study the formal verbal definition:

When a body is immersed in water, the water exerts on the immersed body an upward vertical force (called buoyant force), whose value is equal to the weight of the volume of water displaced by the immersed body.

As mentioned, we begin by identifying the ontology of the process:

Physical entities (expressed as nouns)

Body: material object with mass and volume.

Water: a substance familiar to the students.

Volume of displaced water: corresponds to the volume of the submerged body, since when introduced into the fluid it displaces an amount of water exactly equal to its own volume. To illustrate this, we may use a figurine to recreate the well-known story of Archimedes immersing himself completely (head included) in a bathtub filled to the brim, spilling an amount of water equal to his own volume.

Vector: a mathematical object represented by an arrow, having magnitude (the length of the arrow), direction, and sense. Vectors are added according to the parallelogram rule, resulting in a vector whose effects are equivalent to those of the original vectors. Recall the case in which one donkey plus one donkey equals one and a half donkeys.

Force: a concept or abstraction of something that produces a change in the state of rest or motion of bodies and which has the mathematical nature of a vector.

Weight: the force exerted by gravity on a mass. Being a force, it also has the mathematical nature of a vector.

Causal or situational relations (expressed as verbs and prepositions)

Vertical: a concept that should not be taken as universally understood.

Submerged: the state of a body within water, either partially or totally immersed.

Equilibrium: condition in which the forces applied to a body cancel out, so that the body, in this case, does not move.

To bring these concepts into shared understanding—deconstructing misconceptions and constructing new knowledge where lacking—we prepare a container of appropriate size filled with water and a variety of objects: some that float, some that sink, and some that remain suspended midway. We may use natural items, such as fruits, and artificial ones such as plastic bottles (empty or filled with water), marbles, stones, caps, etc. What matters is that children can experiment with them, observe, compare, and, above all, acquire the concepts that form the ontology, necessary to understand the phenomenon of buoyancy.

Next, in view of the container, we ask pertinent questions: What does it mean to float, to have buoyancy, to have weight? These concepts must be constructed from the actions and sensations of submerging floating objects or pulling them upward in the water—the basis of the well-known naïve formulation of Archimedes' principle that “things weigh less in water.” Through this activity, the foundations are laid for building the shared scenario of the phenomenon (body, water, force, weight, buoyancy, etc.), necessary to collectively travel the path leading to scientific knowledge.

We conclude this section by emphasizing that it is essential for the students and the teacher to share the same mental framework, with its ontology—the concepts involved in the phenomenon under study—and its epistemological dimension—the observations to be made and how they are to be made. With these concepts, some tied to real objects and others to mathematical entities, each student constructs in their imagination a personal space in which to represent the process that leads to Archimedes' principle.

The teacher's art lies in ensuring that all these personal frameworks converge into a single shared one. It is in this mysterious, almost magical, common mental space—imagined and shared—that true teaching takes place. Only then can students' mental representations connect with the teacher's, establishing a common space of thought: the place where, strictly speaking, the extraordinary process of learning occurs.

4. OBSERVATION IS NOT THE SAME AS EXPERIMENTATION

At the conclusion of our exploration, we clarify that observation is not the same as experimentation. In science, it is not enough to superficially observe what happens; an experiment is, in fact, the way in which scientists interrogate nature about what they

wish to know. Therefore, it must be carefully designed so as to corner nature (R. Gomer, 1979), so to speak, leaving it no choice but to respond clearly to the question we pose.

4.1. A QUALITATIVE EXPERIMENT FOR YOUNG CHILDREN

To clearly distinguish between the effects of weight and buoyancy in this context, we propose the following experiment: we construct a kind of submersible hot-air balloon, formed by a small air-inflated balloon, attached with thick thread and adhesive tape to a transparent plastic cup serving as a basket. Several of these devices will be made with balloons of different sizes, allowing us to study the possible effect of volume on the system's behavior in water.

For pedagogical purposes, and to facilitate an initial understanding of the phenomenon, the following idealized model is adopted—as is the case with all scientific models. The total buoyant force is attributed to the effect of the balloon, disregarding the volume of the cup and the marbles; similarly, the entire weight is assigned to the set of marbles, ignoring the weight of the balloon and the air it contains.

This simplification allows us to interpret the system as a model of opposing vertical forces (entirely real), each represented by a vector (a mathematical object): the buoyant force upward, applied at the center of the balloon, and the weight downward, applied at the center of the cup. Both forces will be represented by arrows whose lengths are proportional to their magnitudes, making it clearly visible which of the two predominates.

We then place the balloon attached to the cup on the surface of the water, carefully submerging the assembly so that the cup is filled with water and completely immersed. We release it and begin to add small marbles one by one, counting their number if the students' age allows.

It is important to observe that as the number of marbles increases—and with it the magnitude of the weight vector—the volume of the submerged part of the balloon also increases. This effect should be represented graphically by showing the lengthening of the buoyant force vector as the submerged portion increases. In any equilibrium situation (without external intervention), both vectors—weight and buoyancy—will always have the same length, since the balloon does not move.

As more marbles are added, a point will be reached at which the system remains submerged, floating between two levels of water, in a more or less stable state of equilibrium. Adding one more marble will cause the system to sink to the bottom; removing one marble will cause it to rise toward the surface. If the marbles are too heavy to achieve this equilibrium, lighter objects such as 5- or 10-cent euro coins or even paper clips may be used instead.

At this stage, the advantage of having constructed devices with balloons of different sizes becomes clear. By comparing the size of the different balloons with the number of marbles each can keep floating midway, we can easily reach the conclusion that the larger the volume of the balloon, the greater the weight—or number of marbles—it can hold in equilibrium. We may thus deduce that buoyant force depends on the volume of the balloon. And since buoyancy is equal to the weight it manages to keep suspended (the number of marbles), we can state that the larger the volume of the balloon, the greater the weight it can support while floating.

When a body, in this case the balloon, is submerged in water,

the water exerts on the submerged body an upward vertical force (called buoyant force)

whose value depends on the volume of water displaced by the submerged body (the balloon).

To conclude, we wish to highlight once again that two clearly different types of entities were involved in the experiment: on the one hand, observable physical objects from the real world—such as the balloon, the water, the marbles, the cup, or the string—and, on the other, mathematical objects that exist only in our imagination – or in Plato’s world of ideas, as he himself would say, such as forces and vectors represented by arrows.

And yet, it is precisely these mathematical objects that allow us to describe, explain, and predict the behavior of real bodies! Thanks to them, we can model natural phenomena, anticipate their effects, and grasp the deeper logic that governs the physical world.

4.2. QUANTITATIVE EXPERIMENT

The following experiment aims to help students understand the difference between a qualitative observation and a quantitative law, highlighting that the latter is indispensable for any engineering application (such as building a ship or a submarine), where general or approximate descriptions are not sufficient.

We begin with an empty plastic bottle (i.e., filled with air), with a capacity of one-third to half a liter, floating on the surface of a water-filled container thanks to the buoyant force exerted by the liquid. If we want to submerge it, it is necessary to apply a vertical downward force, which can be clearly felt when performing the operation. The scientific challenge consists precisely in quantifying that force and relating it to the volume of the bottle.

To do so, we gradually place marbles inside the bottle. Unlike the previous experiment with the balloon and the cup, these marbles do not modify the volume of the submerged body, which considerably simplifies the calculations. In doing this, we observe that there is a certain number of marbles with which the bottle remains in equilibrium, floating midway in the water. If the number of marbles is smaller, the bottle rises; if greater, it sinks to the bottom.

From a physical perspective:

- If the buoyant force vector (upward force) is greater than the weight vector, the system rises.
- If the weight exceeds the buoyant force, the system sinks.
- In equilibrium, both vectors have the same magnitude and opposite directions.

This situation can be represented graphically, as in the previous case, with arrows: one upward arrow starting from the center of volume of the bottle (buoyant force) and another downward arrow from its center of mass (weight). At the equilibrium point, both arrows have the same length, which indicates that the magnitude of buoyancy is equal to the total weight of the bottle plus the marbles.

Keeping in the container the bottle with just enough marbles so that buoyancy equals weight, we fill an identical bottle with water, making sure that no air bubbles remain, and submerge it alongside the first. We will see that both remain in equilibrium, floating

midway. If buoyancy is the same, then weight must also necessarily be the same (by logical deduction).

If we determine, using a kitchen scale, the weight of the bottle with marbles when it remains midway and the weight of a bottle completely filled with water, we will verify that they coincide: the value of buoyancy is equal to the weight of the water that fits into the bottle, that is, the weight of a volume of water equal to the volume of the bottle.

When a body is submerged in water, the water exerts on the submerged body an upward vertical force (called buoyant force) whose value is equal to the weight of the volume of water displaced by the submerged body.

4.3. ASSIMILATION EXPERIMENT

To reinforce this conclusion and to show that buoyancy does not depend on the shape or material of bodies, a simple and replicable check is proposed:

- Fill several balloons of different sizes and shapes with water (ensuring that no air remains inside).
- Submerge them in a container of water.
- Fill several thin plastic bottles of different sizes with water and submerge them in the container as well.

It will be observed that, regardless of their size, all the balloons remain suspended midway, just as the bottles do. This fact confirms that the buoyant force exerted by the water on the submerged bottle or balloon filled with water is equal to the weight of the water-filled bottle or balloon, independently of their size, material, or shape. In this way, Archimedes' principle has been assimilated into a body of prior knowledge already available.

4.4. THOUGHT EXPERIMENT

The final type of experiment we will present is the thought experiment, also called the *experimentum mentale*, a particularly powerful form of reasoning frequently used throughout the history of science. The exercise with water-filled balloons leads us directly to Archimedes' thought experiment, described by Vitruvius, a Roman engineer of the 1st century BC, in his work *De Architectura* (Book IX, Chapter 9).

Archimedes had observed that the water in ponds, in the absence of winds or disturbing elements, remained in perfect equilibrium. Immersing himself with his imagination into one of them, he mentally isolated a spherical volume of water located at the center of the pond, as if it were an invisible balloon whose "skin" was purely imaginary. This

volume had a definite weight, which could be represented by a force vector directed downward.

However, since the water in the pond was at rest, that volume could neither sink nor rise. Therefore, Archimedes reasoned, the rest of the water must exert on that volume an opposite force, directed upward and equal in magnitude to its weight. This was the necessary condition for the system to remain in equilibrium, for the water not to move.

The result follows almost self-evidently: if the water in that imagined volume is removed and replaced by any other substance—for example, a sphere of gold—the buoyant force exerted by the surrounding water will remain the same, since it depends solely on the displaced volume, not on the material introduced. The water, ignorant of the content of the substituted volume, exerts on it a force equal to the weight of the water that originally occupied that space.

And thus we arrive, by reasoning, at the same conclusion we reached through experiments and measurements.

To conclude this section, we would like to mention some of the most influential thought experiments in the history of physics:

- The ideal Carnot engine (Sadi Carnot, 1824) – Thermodynamics
- Maxwell’s demon (James Clerk Maxwell, 1867) – Thermodynamics and information
- Light rays on a moving train (Albert Einstein, 1905) – Special relativity
- Einstein’s elevator (Albert Einstein, 1907–1915) – General relativity
- The Elitzur–Vaidman bomb (Avshalom Elitzur and Lev Vaidman, 1993) – Quantum mechanics and interaction-free interference

All of them, in one way or another, gave rise to paradigm shifts in our way of understanding nature.

Although not all thought experiments are appropriate for students in the earliest stages of education, their comprehension is essential for teachers, since they reveal the astonishing parallelism between the behavior of the physical world and the logic of

human thought. As Einstein wrote: “*The most incomprehensible thing about the universe is that it is comprehensible*” (Einstein, 1936). And as Plato said, the gods use only geometry.

5. SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM SHIFTS IN THE CLASSROOM AND THEIR CORRELATION WITH STUDENTS’ COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT

The history of science is punctuated by milestones that mark true revolutions in the way the real world is conceptualized—what Thomas Kuhn (1962) called *scientific revolutions*, characterized by profound paradigm shifts. These changes are not limited to simple adjustments; they entail radical transformations in ontology (the nature of entities considered real) and epistemology (the valid methods for knowing them). What is considered to exist changes—for example, particles come to be understood as waves, and vice versa; what can be measured changes; the questions that make sense to ask change; and the appropriate procedures to answer them also change.

This historical dynamic bears surprising analogies to the evolution of children’s thought described by Jean Piaget, which also progresses through stages characterized by specific modes of reasoning and world conception (Piaget, 1975). According to Piaget, the transition from one stage to another occurs through two fundamental processes: disequilibrium, which arises when a prior mental *scheme* is insufficient to explain a new experience, and accommodation, through which the subject reorganizes or modifies their *schemes* to integrate that experience.

The correspondence with Kuhn’s concepts is remarkable. Normal science resembles the period of cognitive equilibrium: a scientific community works within a stable paradigm. The appearance of an anomaly in scientific societies is equivalent to Piaget’s disequilibrium: the mismatch between consolidated knowledge and observed facts, results that do not fit the prevailing paradigm. Crisis emerges when anomalies accumulate and undermine confidence in the existing conceptual framework—what Piaget would call disequilibrium in individuals. Finally, a scientific revolution in societies corresponds to the process of accommodation in humans: the old paradigm is abandoned, and a new one is adopted, with a new ontology, new rules, and new ways of looking at the world. and the period of new science begins.

5.1. THE CASE OF LIGHT: FROM NEWTON TO YOUNG

The evolution of the concept of light—from Newton’s corpuscular model to Huygens’ wave theory—constitutes an excellent example of a paradigm shift in the history of science, with clear implications for teaching. Such conceptual transformations foster the development of metacognition, that is, the ability to observe and reflect on one’s own learning process. It is like having a mind that supervises the mind: it allows recognition of how one learns, what strategies are used, when errors occur, and how they can be

corrected. And this process is greatly facilitated when changes in the way the world is seen are evident.

For this reason, even if only schematically, it is useful to describe some of these historical milestones, since knowledge of them makes their didactic presentation easier.

In the mechanistic paradigm proposed by Newton in 1704, a ray of light was conceived as a stream of luminous corpuscles, material and perfectly elastic, traveling in a straight line. This model explained phenomena such as reflection, refraction, geometrical optics, and color physics, and fit fully into the classical physics of the 17th century. Because of its simplicity and its agreement with everyday experience, this paradigm is particularly well suited to the preoperational stage of thought (ages 2–7), without the need to introduce more abstract notions.

However, Newton himself observed phenomena that did not fit his model, such as Newton's rings, circular patterns appearing when a plano-convex lens was placed on a flat glass surface. This experimental result generated a disequilibrium in normal science, since it did not align with the principles of the corpuscular model. Instead of accepting the wave theory that Huygens had proposed in 1678—according to which light propagates as a wave through the ether—Newton attempted to maintain his theory by introducing ambiguous explanations such as *fits*, an alternating disposition of corpuscles to reflect or refract depending on their prior trajectory, as if they somehow retained a memory of the path traveled.

This attempt to preserve the paradigm without modifying its ontology left optics in a state of conceptual crisis that persisted for more than a century. Finally, in the 19th century, scientists such as Thomas Young, with his double-slit diffraction experiment (1801), and Augustin-Jean Fresnel (1816–1821), through polarization phenomena, demonstrated that these results could only be understood if light was a transverse wave (and *not longitudinal* like sound, as had been assumed since Huygens). In 1818, Fresnel's wave theory was evaluated by the French Academy and experimentally confirmed by François Arago.

Fresnel's contributions were fundamental for the subsequent development of the modern conception of light as an electromagnetic wave, formulated by James Clerk Maxwell in 1865, who unified electricity, magnetism, and optics within a single wave-based theoretical framework.

This process marked one of the greatest paradigm shifts in the history of optics: light ceased to be conceived as a succession of particles of different colors and came to be understood as a wave phenomenon with waves of different frequencies.

5.2. THE WAVE PARADIGM IN THE CLASSROOM

The wave model can be introduced in an adapted way from the age of 7, coinciding with the onset of concrete operational thought, as described by Piaget. At this stage, children are already capable of establishing stable causal relationships, making logical classifications, and using analogies to build coherent explanations.

As we have already noted, one cannot wait until students are fully able to understand what is being explained before beginning to explain it. Just as one learns to speak by listening and speaking, one learns science by experimenting, testing models, and confronting questions that cannot yet be answered with existing knowledge.

One effective way to work on this concept in the classroom is to reproduce Young's experiment. For this, we use two slits formed by three teeth of a fine-toothed comb (like a lice comb) isolated with tape, and a low-power red laser pointer. Projecting the light onto a screen generates interference fringes that spark students' curiosity. At this stage, the goal is not to introduce the physical formalism of the wave model but to provoke a question that opens the door to conceptual change.

As Richard Feynman expressed in *The Feynman Lectures on Physics, Vol. III*: “*The double-slit experiment has in it the heart of quantum mechanics. In reality, it contains the only mystery.*”

How can it be that light produces bright and dark bands when one should expect to see the shadow of the central tooth that separates the slits?

To facilitate the intuitive construction of the wave model, the phenomenon is compared to water waves: when two wave sources are generated, an analogous interference pattern is observed. This type of *analogical reasoning* is characteristic of concrete operational thought: if two phenomena produce the same effects, it is reasonable to assume that they share some causal mechanism.

Finally, the understanding of the new paradigm can be reinforced with linear polarization experiments, which can be easily carried out using accessible materials. In this way, students progressively assimilate the wave model without the need for mathematical formalism, while developing increasing metacognitive awareness of how scientific knowledge is constructed.

Thus, teaching becomes not merely the transmission of content, but a guided reconstruction of the paradigm shifts that structure the history of scientific thought—shifts that can be reflected upon in order to examine the limits of validity and applicability of each theory.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the discovery of the photoelectric effect by Hertz—the emission of electrons by certain metals when illuminated, which we have sometimes demonstrated in our courses—revealed a behavior that could not be explained by the wave model of light, introducing a new disequilibrium into normal science based on the wave theory of light. In 1905, Einstein proposed that light is composed of *quanta*, or discrete packets of energy, which we now call *photons*.

This new model did not revive the old corpuscular idea, but rather introduced a paradigm entirely different from Newton's. Whereas Newtonian corpuscles were classical material particles, with mass and well-defined trajectories, Einstein's photons are quantum entities, massless, behaving like particles only at the moment of interaction, and whose energy depends on the frequency of light, not its intensity.

The photon does not contradict the wave model but complements it within *a new dual vision*: light is neither particle nor wave, but something that behaves as a wave or as a particle depending on the question asked of it, depending on the experiment. This perspective on the nature of things—whose ultimate answer lies beyond our reach—marked a paradigm shift and opened the way to modern physics.

6. GENDER AND INCLUSION IN LANGUAGE

Language is not only a means of communication but also a symbolic system that organizes experience and shapes the perception of reality. From the perspective of the *Sapir-Whorf hypothesis*, linguistic structure is not neutral: while it reflects the social world, it also molds it and constrains the possibilities of thought and action. Within this framework, the analysis of sexist language becomes highly relevant, since its persistence reproduces gender inequalities, limits the visibility of certain groups, and perpetuates hierarchical conceptions in social, professional, and cultural domains.

6.1. LANGUAGE AND THE ONTOGENY OF WORLD REPRESENTATION

Changes in language cannot be understood as mere terminological substitutions but as genuine paradigmatic transformations. Just as in the scientific revolutions described by

Thomas Kuhn (1962), the introduction of new terms and concepts triggers a reorganization of the interpretative framework of reality. Similarly, in Piaget's model of cognitive development (1936/1977), these processes resemble dynamics of disequilibrium and accommodation, in which preexisting schemes are questioned and reorganized. In the case of inclusion and gender, transforming the social reality represented by language necessarily requires transforming the conceptual structures that language itself embodies.

Childhood represents a privileged stage for introducing such transformations. At this age, language acquisition—and with it, the conceptual universe it conveys—is especially permeable. Introducing inclusive language early in life makes it possible to construct more egalitarian worldviews and to interrupt the intergenerational transmission of sexist stereotypes.

In professional and academic contexts, the use of expressions such as *mankind*, *chairman*, or *housewife* reflects and reinforces the traditional association between authority, competence, and masculinity, as opposed to caregiving and domestic roles traditionally assigned to femininity. Likewise, the distinction between *actor* and *actress*, or the perception of some professions as “male” (engineer, doctor) and others as “female” (nurse, secretary), shapes vocational aspirations and limits opportunities for personal and professional development.

The gradual shift toward neutral forms—*humankind*, *chairperson*, *firefighter*, *police officer*, *server*—constitutes a linguistic mechanism that helps to mitigate the reproduction of stereotypes. This process is far from trivial: it has a direct impact on social cognition by modifying the reference frameworks that guide the attribution of roles and competences.

Empirical evidence shows that sexist language contributes to structural phenomena such as the “glass ceiling,” understood as the invisible barrier that prevents women from reaching positions of power and prestige. Attributing women's achievements to luck or external circumstances, rather than to their competence and effort, reveals a gender bias that undermines the social recognition of female ability. As Bourdieu (1991) argues, language functions as an instrument of symbolic power that legitimizes or delegitimizes social realities, and in this case, serves to reproduce inequalities in the distribution of resources, prestige, and opportunities.

6.2. SOCIAL INERTIA TO CHANGE

The analysis of sexist language confirms that linguistic change is inseparable from social change. Transformations toward inclusive terminology must be understood as genuine processes of *conceptual revolution*, comparable to scientific paradigm shifts and to the cognitive restructuring that occurs during childhood development. The implementation of inclusive language in early education, as well as in professional and social contexts, not only corrects a linguistic asymmetry but also contributes to the construction of more egalitarian societies. Consequently, the study of sexist language cannot be reduced to a semantic issue; it constitutes a central field of inquiry for

understanding the symbolic mechanisms that sustain gender inequality and for designing strategies of cultural transformation.

The modification of connotative biases does not occur automatically. On the contrary, it requires processes of re-signification that often involve social tensions comparable to those described by Kuhn (1962) in his analysis of scientific revolutions. Just as scientific paradigms resist change until a cumulative crisis of anomalies arises, social meanings frequently react with hostility to change, despite empirical evidence or criticism. Only through conflictive processes of cultural transformation is it possible to replace a dominant semantic network with an alternative one, as occurs in shifts of perspective on gender, class, or race. This analogy with Kuhnian paradigm shifts underscores the epistemological dimension of the struggle for meaning: it is not merely about naming differently, but about perceiving reality through new lenses. Language, thus conceived, does not simply mirror reality but actively participates in its reconfiguration.

6.3. SCIENCE CANNOT BE SEXIST

Science, as a form of knowledge grounded in observation and experimentation, aspires to objectivity. Yet it is not immune to the social, political, and cultural contexts in which it is produced. Within the Western scientific tradition—with roots in the Aristotelian corpus—an androcentric bias has been perpetuated for centuries, systematically excluding women from the spaces of knowledge creation and transmission, both as subjects and as objects of inquiry.

From the outset, women were denied access to schools, academies, and universities. They were not allowed to learn Latin, the *lingua franca* of science and culture, which excluded them from scientific discourse. Even the great thinkers who challenged established doctrines failed to recognize this structural injustice. The Enlightenment, the French Revolution, and the U.S. Constitution, despite their ideals of equality, ignored women's rights.

Some courageous voices, such as Mary Wollstonecraft (*A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*, 1792) and Olympe de Gouges (*Déclaration des droits de la femme et de la citoyenne*, 1791), denounced this exclusion, but they were silenced or, at best, ignored. It was not until the 19th century that some universities began admitting women, and suffragist movements paved the way toward greater social and political participation.

During the 20th century, feminist thought sought to identify and reconstruct the role of women as active agents in the history of science, adopting different theoretical approaches, most of them neglected by official academia. In the 1970s, the first critical voices emerged, analyzing the construction of knowledge from a gender perspective. Sandra Harding (1991), Evelyn Fox Keller (1985), and Londa Schiebinger (1989, 1991), among others, considered gender as an analytical category that influences the ways in which knowledge is produced, communicated, and applied.

Several authors demonstrated the necessity of addressing the history of knowledge through a gender perspective in order to approach reality more accurately. To

understand history without acknowledging the role of women is like trying to explain the functioning of a clock without considering some of the gears that make it work.

Free from prejudices and cultural biases, many studies have highlighted the scientific contributions of women who were rendered invisible throughout history, denouncing the sexist assumptions of academia. For instance, Rosalind Franklin's crucial X-ray diffraction images made possible the discovery of the DNA double helix, yet her role was long overshadowed by the fame of Watson and Crick. Similarly, Nettie Stevens identified the XY sex-determination system, but her discovery was attributed for decades to her male contemporaries. Lise Meitner, who provided the theoretical explanation for nuclear fission, was excluded from the Nobel Prize awarded to her collaborator Otto Hahn. More recently, Jocelyn Bell Burnell discovered the first radio pulsars, a breakthrough that earned the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1974—but it was awarded only to her male supervisor. These and many other cases illustrate how structural biases in academia have systematically marginalized women, despite their decisive contributions to the advancement of science.

Including women's scientific achievements in textbooks can help foster scientific vocations; but more importantly, it allows the narrative to align more closely with reality and, therefore, to be more credible. Presenting the success stories of women such as Marie Curie, awarded two Nobel Prizes in Physics and Chemistry; Rita Levi-Montalcini, Nobel Prize in Medicine; or Jennifer Doudna and Emmanuelle Charpentier, Nobel Prize in Chemistry for the development of CRISPR gene-editing, provides powerful role models for girls who wish to become scientists, demonstrating that excellence and recognition are within their reach.

Today, in the 21st century, we continue to face this problem from new interdisciplinary perspectives, recognizing that science is not neutral and that the full inclusion of women in research and teaching remains an unfinished task. The issue is highly complex, and it is essential to keep it in mind in education to avoid, even unintentionally, transmitting biased values that perpetuate the gender gap.

7. CONCLUSION

This article has argued that science education should be conceived as the learning of a specific language, a second language that allows us to represent and understand reality differently from everyday language. As in any language, learning begins with simple fragments of experience, which can be translated into accessible words and concepts, and progresses toward more complex structures that require new meanings and symbolic tools to be expressed.

The developmental process of individuals or societies throughout history can be imagined as the growth of the layers of an onion, where each new layer reveals a more detailed knowledge of reality. Each transition between layers implies a point of wonder, a form of cognitive disequilibrium—in Piaget's terms—or a crisis, like those Kuhn described in scientific revolutions. These moments of strangeness should be

pedagogically leveraged as drivers of learning: they activate curiosity, foster distrust of students' prior models, and push them to construct new explanatory frameworks.

In the division we have proposed of the history of science according to its paradigms—which assign different meanings to apparently identical phenomena—light is first interpreted as a corpuscle in the Newtonian tradition, later as a wave in the theories of Huygens, Young, Fresnel, and Maxwell, and finally, in the 20th century, as a quantum entity with wave–particle duality, whose observed behavior depends on the type of experiment performed. If we could revisit this history in dialogue with the scientists of each era, we would need to use the same words with different meanings, in the same way that we use different forms of language to communicate with a three-year-old, a seven-year-old, a twelve-year-old, or a seventeen-year-old. Something similar happens with the electron: initially discovered as a particle, it was soon recognized to have wave-like properties, until the current quantum formulation, in which it is not a matter of “being” one thing or another, but of manifesting different properties depending on how it is observed. Thus, in both the historical evolution of science and in the cognitive development of individuals, paradigm shifts involve profound transformations in language and, therefore, in the categories with which we describe reality.

Teaching science in this way is not about transmitting finished theories but about showing how they are built, when they apply, and why they change. The key lies in helping students understand that each theory has a field of validity, and that the value of a theory does not reside in its absolute truth, but in its usefulness within certain limits. To reach Mars, Newtonian mechanics suffices; but to build a transistor or a laser, we need quantum mechanics. To understand this is to understand the very nature of science: a language in constant evolution, modeling the world according to the questions we ask and the instruments we have to answer them.

To conclude this series of articles, we would like to recall Carl Sagan's words in an interview with Charlie Rose in May 1996, in which he delved into the critical role of science as a way of thinking and as a defense against deception and manipulation:

“Science is more than a body of knowledge; it is a way of thinking. It is a way of skeptically interrogating the universe. If we are not able to ask skeptical questions, to interrogate those who tell us that something is true, to be skeptical of those in authority, then we're up for grabs for the next charlatan—political or religious—who comes ambling along.”

8.- REFERENCES

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PARADIGMS OF LIGHT AND THEIR CORRESPONDENCE WITH PIAGET'S STAGES

Paradigm of light	Cognitive stage (Piaget)	Didactic description
Corpuscular (Newton, 1704)	Preoperational thought (2–7 years)	Intuitive explanation: light consists of particles traveling in straight lines. Suitable for everyday experience and concrete thinking.
Wave (Huygens, Young, Fresnel, 1678–1821)	Concrete operations (7–11 years)	Use of analogies (water waves) to understand phenomena such as interference and

		diffraction. Development of logical causality.
Quantum (Einstein, 1905)	Formal operations (12+ years)	Light behaves as a wave or as a particle depending on the experiment. Requires abstract thought and handling of conceptual dualities.
